

Cell force identification

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a method for identification of cell forces. We propose both a local and non-local method. The former assumes rotation free field of surface tractions, while the latter introduces an intrinsic length scale parameter, such that cells can locally apply a moment on the material surface. This paper focuses attention on a numerical aspect of force identification without investigating, at this stage, the true nature of that forces.

Key Words: Force identification, Finite elements

1. Introduction

The forces exerted by living cells on a surface can be identified experimentally by observing displacements in the material. These displacements can, for example, be measured by tracking beads embedded in a flexible gel substrate on which the cells are cultured.

Figure 1: Identification of cell forces

This work builds on a substantial number of papers on force identification, and in particular the calculation of forces exerted by cells. For example [1], where a semi-analytical approach is used, applying the fundamental solution to construct an objective function which is minimised to find cell tractions. In [1], the solution space is transformed using a Fourier transform so that the problem can be solved efficiently. In this paper, a similar approach to the one proposed in [2] is used, overcoming the limitations of the method proposed in [1], where here finite element method can be used. Such an approach enables heterogeneous materials, nonlinear behaviour and complex geometries to be taken into account.

In the following, we analyse the displacements observed on an arbitrary surface, inside or on a body, which in general will be different from the surface where tractions are applied. In the particular problem considered here, a body is covered by a transparent thin, but stiff gel layer. Below that layer is a large volume of soft gel. The movement of beads is recorded at the interface of the two layers. No assumption is made on the homogeneity of the material and the solution scheme presented could be applied to a nonlinear material response which evolves in time, see Figure 1.

2. Local rotation-free formulation

The problem of force identification can be mathematically described by a constrained minimisation problem, as follows

$$\begin{cases} \min J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} \\ \operatorname{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u})] = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } V \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}) = \boldsymbol{\rho} \quad \text{on } S_\rho, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} are unknown displacements in the body, \mathbf{u}_d are observed displacements on the surface S_u and $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ are unknown tractions on the given surface S_ρ . Note that expressions of the form $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})_V$ and $(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v})_{S_u}$ are scalar products of functions \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{v} in the volume V and on the surface S_u respectively. The second and third equations are constraints, expressing linear momentum conservation and balance of internal material forces with externally applied cell forces $\boldsymbol{\rho}$. Operator S in the first term in equation (1) is a penalty controlling how well displacements in the body \mathbf{u} satisfy measured displacements \mathbf{u}_d . For simplicity, S can be understood as a diagonal matrix scaled by a penalty parameter ϵ_u . The second term in the objective function controls tractions $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ and is required to ensure that the problem is well posed. Applying the standard Lagrange multiplier method, we get

$$\begin{cases} \min J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} + (\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}, \operatorname{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}])_V \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\rho} \quad \text{on } S_\rho \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ is the Lagrange multiplier. Differentiating the first equation by parts and using the second constraint, leads to:

$$J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} + (\operatorname{grad}[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}], \boldsymbol{\sigma})_V - (\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho}. \quad (3)$$

where the Neumann boundary condition is enforced in a weak sense. Expressing the material relationship as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathcal{A}(\operatorname{grad}[\mathbf{u}])^s \quad (4)$$

and using the symmetry of operator \mathcal{A} , we get

$$J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\Upsilon}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} + (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \operatorname{grad}[\mathbf{u}])_V - (\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} \quad (5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \mathcal{A}(\operatorname{grad}[\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}])^s$. Finding the minimum of (5), we get the Euler equations in the following form

$$\begin{cases} (S\mathbf{u}, \delta\mathbf{u})_{S_u} + (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \operatorname{grad}[\delta\mathbf{u}])_V = 0 \\ (\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \operatorname{grad}[\delta\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}])_V - (\boldsymbol{\rho}, \delta\boldsymbol{\Upsilon})_{S_\rho} = 0 \\ (\epsilon_\rho\boldsymbol{\rho}, \delta\boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} - (\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}, \delta\boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Applying finite element discretization, the above equations are expressed as a system of linear algebraic equations, suitable for computer analysis

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{K}_{u\Upsilon} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{K}_{\Upsilon u} & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{B}^T \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \boldsymbol{\Upsilon} \\ \boldsymbol{\rho} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}\mathbf{u}_d \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The field of Lagrange multipliers $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}$ can be interpreted here as displacements in the body resulting from displacements given on the surface S_u , without surface tractions present. Swapping first two rows, we finally get

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{\Upsilon u} & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{B}^T \\ \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{K}_{u\Upsilon} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ \boldsymbol{\Upsilon} \\ \boldsymbol{\rho} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{S}\mathbf{u}_d \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The ϵ_u and ϵ_ρ are model parameters. As a rule of thumb, ϵ_u is large, and ϵ_ρ is small. Since the body only experiences forces due to the cells attached to the body surface S_ρ , it is not subject to rigid body motion. It is assumed that forces are generated by cells, considered here as 2D objects and, as a result, only tangential forces can be produced by those forces if the surface is planar. For non-planar surfaces additional force normal to the surface are present, and the magnitude of this force could be calculated purely from geometrical considerations. Thus, additional physical equations are not needed.

Assuming that straight and pre-stressed fibres within cells generate the forces exerted by the cell on the substrate, it can be inferred that the force field is rotation-free. Therefore, these forces can be expressed in terms of a scalar potential field ϕ as follows

$$\boldsymbol{\rho} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \quad (9)$$

Thus, it is possible to solve for the scalar potential field, rather than the vector force field.

3. Non-local, i.e. weakly enforced rotation-free formulation

Here the generalisation of the local model to a weakly enforced rotation-free cell force field is considered. This generalisation is a consequence of the observation that cell has some small but finite size. Moreover, a cell has a complex pre-stressed structure which can transfer shear forces.

This problem is defined similarly to the local version. However, this time we add the additional non-local term,

$$\begin{cases} \min J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho} - l^2 \operatorname{div}^s[\operatorname{curl}^s[\boldsymbol{\rho}]])_{S_\rho} \\ \operatorname{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u})] = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } V \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\rho} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Reformulating this we have

$$\begin{cases} \min J(\mathbf{u}, \boldsymbol{\rho}) = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d, S(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d))_{S_u} + \frac{\epsilon_\rho}{2}(\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} + \frac{\epsilon_l^{-1}}{2}(\operatorname{curl}^s[\boldsymbol{\rho}], \operatorname{curl}^s[\boldsymbol{\rho}])_{S_\rho} \\ \operatorname{div}[\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u})] = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{in } V \\ \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\rho} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where parameter ϵ_l controls the rotation-free term. As this parameter approaches zero, this formulation converges to the local variant presented above. Applying the same procedure as before, the set of Euler equations is derived

$$\begin{cases} (S\mathbf{u}, \delta\mathbf{u})_{S_u} + (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}, \operatorname{grad}[\delta\mathbf{u}])_V = 0 \\ (\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \operatorname{grad}[\delta\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}])_V - (\boldsymbol{\rho}, \delta\boldsymbol{\Upsilon})_{S_\rho} = 0 \\ (\epsilon_\rho \boldsymbol{\rho}, \delta\boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} + \epsilon_l^{-1}(\operatorname{curl}^s[\boldsymbol{\rho}], \operatorname{curl}^s[\delta\boldsymbol{\rho}])_{S_\rho} - (\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}, \delta\boldsymbol{\rho})_{S_\rho} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

4. Finite element approximation

For the local version, standard piecewise continuous polynomials can be applied as an approximation basis. In general, functions approximating displacements \mathbf{u}^h , Lagrange multipliers $\boldsymbol{\Upsilon}^h$ and potential field ϕ^h have to belong to the standard finite dimensions Hilbert space, $H^1(V)$ for displacements and $H^1(S_\rho)$ for the potential field. Note that $\boldsymbol{\rho}^h$ is obtained by taking the gradient of the potential field ϕ^h .

For the non-local version, it is required that the approximation of tractions $\boldsymbol{\rho}^h$ belongs to a finite vectorial space such that the tangential component of tractions is piecewise continuous, i.e. tractions belong to $H(\operatorname{curl}, S_\rho)$ space.

In this work, complexities related to the construction of approximation spaces, integration of element matrices, problem assembly and pre- and post- processing are implemented in general purpose finite element code MoFEM [3]. Hierarchical approximation bases with an arbitrary polynomial order on the tetrahedron, prism or triangle element is used. Prism elements are used to model the very thin gel layer, see Figure 1.

5. Iterative solver and block preconditioner

In this implementation, the block structure of the matrix is utilised and solved using the PETSc block preconditioner with GEMREs solver [4]. The functionality of PETSc is enabled by the generic and multi-purpose MoFEM implementation of Discrete Manager Interface.

The problem discussed here has three unique matrices, i.e. \mathbf{S} , \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{B} . Such a problem can be solved efficiently applying Jacobi or Gauss-Seidel on matrix blocks or by applying Schur complement when convenient, see [5].

Utilising the capabilities of MoFEM and PETSc, the problem is decomposed on two nested sub-problems, which conveniently can be expressed by matrices $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$, as follows,

$$\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{X}} & \bar{\mathbf{V}} \\ \bar{\mathbf{H}} & \bar{\mathbf{D}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \text{where } \bar{\mathbf{X}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{S} & \mathbf{K} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{V}} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{B}^T \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{H}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{B}^T \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

The problem associated with matrix $\bar{\bar{\mathbf{A}}}$ is used applying Shur complement pre-conditioner, whereas the nested sub-problem associated with matrix $\bar{\mathbf{X}}$ is solved using block Gauss-Seidel solver. With this approach, only matrixes \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{B} are stored physically in memory and matrix \mathbf{K} is only factored once. This enables efficient and robust solution for large systems, see example in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Example of cell force identification using the non-local variant of the formulation.

6. Summary

This paper has briefly introduced a methodology for identifying tractions exerted by cell forces. The unknown fields are approximated using the finite element method and solved with an iterative block solver. Three novelties are introduced in this paper. First, the method is generalised to be applied for heterogeneous (two layered) material. Second, a non-local variant is derived, and finally, an efficient and robust solution technique is proposed. Moreover, hierarchical and heterogeneous approximation bases of arbitrary order are used.

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